

The application of the “Q-Split” tool in assessing split incentives for rural energy renovations

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About RENOVERTY

RENOVERTY will foster energy efficiency building upgrades in the Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), South-eastern Europe (SEE) countries, as well as Southern European countries (SE), by setting the methodological and practical framework to build renovation roadmaps of vulnerable rural districts in a financially viable and socially just manner.

Specifically, the project aims to deliver tools and resources to support local and regional actors to build and execute operational single or multi-household roadmaps for rural areas. A scalable model will also be created to ensure the wide geographical replicability and implementation of the roadmaps by different actors at the EU level. Strategically, the project will contribute to minimising logistical, financial, administrative, and legal burdens caused by a complex and multi-stakeholder home renovation process. Additionally, RENOVERTY will ensure that building retrofits consider the social dimension by incorporating security, comfort, and improved accessibility in the roadmaps to further improve the quality of life of vulnerable populations.

Over the project’s three years, seven pilots located in Sveta Nedelja (Croatia), Tartu (Estonia), Bükk-Mak & Somló-Marcalmente-Bakonyalja Leader (Hungary), Zasavje (Slovenia), Parma (Italy), Coimbra (Portugal), and Osona (Spain) will implement the roadmaps, while wider integration of rural and peri-urban development is foreseen in the long run.

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List of Abbreviations

CEE	Central Eastern Europe
DREEM	Dynamic high-Resolution dE-mand-side Management
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
MFH	Multi-family house
NPV	Net Present Value
REERs	Rural Energy Efficiency Roadmaps
SE	Southern Europe
SEE	Southern Eastern Europe
SFH	Single-family house

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1. Introduction

Energy poverty remains a persistent and multifaceted challenge across Europe, with rural areas facing distinct and often overlooked vulnerabilities. Lower household incomes, ageing and inefficient housing stock, as well as limited policy attention compound the difficulties experienced by rural citizens [1]. A growing body of evidence indicates that rural areas are especially at risk of being left behind in the pursuit of a clean and just energy transition, despite facing a higher likelihood of poverty and energy-related challenges [2], [3], [4].

This situation is particularly acute in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), South-Eastern Europe (SEE), and Southern Europe (SE), where exposure to energy poverty is especially widespread [5], [6]. In response, the RENOVERTY project aims to promote energy-efficient building upgrades in these regions by establishing a methodological and practical framework for developing renovation roadmaps in vulnerable rural districts- ensuring that these are both financially viable and socially just.

To achieve this, RENOVERTY is collaborating with stakeholders across the rural energy efficiency renovation value chain in several pilot regions throughout the EU- Sveta Nedelja (Croatia), Tartu (Estonia), Bükk-Mak & Somló-Marcalmente-Bakonyalja Leader (Hungary), Zasavje (Slovenia), Parma (Italy), Coimbra (Portugal), and Osona (Spain). Together, they are co-creating tailored Rural Energy Efficiency Roadmaps (REERs) that reflect the specific socio-economic and housing contexts of each region, ensuring that the proposed interventions are both context-sensitive and practically implementable.

Although rental properties are typically more prominent in urban settings, interactions with pilot partners during the co-creation of the project' REERs revealed that private renting is also present in rural areas, specifically in the regions of Osona (Spain), Zasavje (Slovenia), and Tartu (Estonia).

This poses a significant challenge for carrying out rural renovations, as those living in rented dwellings often face additional barriers in increasing the energy efficiency of their housing compared to homeowners. Most notably, they encounter and must overcome the "split incentives" challenge, a situation in which landlords are expected to finance energy upgrades, while tenants receive the primary benefits [7]. This misalignment of costs and rewards can discourage investment and hinder renovation efforts.

To address this challenge, the "**Q-Split**" (**Quantification of Split Incentives**) tool [8], originally developed under the Horizon 2020 [ENPOR project](#), has been expanded and adapted within RENOVERTY to support the fair and effective design of energy renovation strategies in rural private rented housing. The tool enables the assessment of how costs and benefits from renovation measures can be distributed between landlords and tenants, providing an evidence base to inform equitable financing mechanisms and policy recommendations.

A key aim of this report is to present insights from the application of the Q-SpliT tool in the three RENOVERTY pilot regions where private renting is identified. The findings could serve as a valuable input towards the finalisation of the project's REERs, by quantifying split incentives associated with priority renovation measures and supporting the development of socially just, financially viable renovation solutions tailored to the needs of rural households.

2. Methodological background of the tool

As outlined in the introductory report of the Q-SpliT tool, developed within the Horizon 2020 ENPOR project [8], the methodological background of the tool is based on the quantification of energy savings and positive externalities associated with specific energy efficiency interventions [8].

2.1 Quantification of energy savings

For the quantification of energy savings, the tool either applies a set of predefined assumptions tailored to each case study or allows users to provide relevant input data.

The assumptions vary by country and include parameters such as the average energy consumption of the building in kWh/m², the percentage of space heating and cooling energy consumption, and the energy prices. Based on user inputs, namely country, year of construction, building area (m²), and heating source, the tool selects the appropriate energy saving rate for each energy efficiency scenario and estimates the expected reductions in heating and cooling energy consumption, both in kWh and in monetary terms (€).

In the context of the RENOVERTY project, the tool is applied using the second option, whereby context-specific data on building energy consumption and potential energy savings are sourced from the application of the **Dynamic high-Resolution dE-mand-side Management (DREEM)** model in the project's regions, as outlined in Apostoliotis et al. (2024) [9]. DREEM is a fully integrated simulation model of energy demand and demand-side management in the building sector [10]. Within the RENOVERTY project, DREEM has been employed to provide an evaluation framework on the application of different energy efficiency measures in households in the project's pilot regions [9].

2.2 Quantification of the positive externalities

Energy efficiency investments primarily reduce energy consumption. Nevertheless, they also contribute to addressing broader challenges such as energy supply security, climate change, employment. Beyond any direct outcomes, the implementation of energy efficiency measures can yield additional socio-economic and environmental benefits, often referred to as "non-energy" effects or externalities.

Within the framework of the Q-Split tool, **four types of externalities** are assessed: (i) environmental impacts, (ii) macroeconomic impacts (e.g., changes in Gross Domestic Product), (iii) increases in building value, and (iv) other multiple benefits (e.g., enhanced comfort and health conditions). The first two categories, i.e., environmental and macroeconomic impacts, are considered to generate broad societal benefits and are thus assumed to affect both landlords and tenants equally. In contrast, the increase in building value primarily benefits landlords, while the multiple benefits, such as improved indoor comfort and health outcomes, are benefiting tenants.

2.3 Calculation of the split incentive gap

2.3.1 Estimating benefits for landlords and tenants

The Q-Split tool calculates the split incentive gap on the rental price, which is defined as **the discrepancy between the rental price increase expected by the landlords (based on their share of investment and benefits) and the rental price increase that can be considered fair from the tenant’s perspective, based on their share of benefits and participation in the investment**. More specifically, the split incentive gap is defined by calculating the Net Present Value (NPV) of the benefits and investment participation of both landlords and tenants in energy efficiency interventions.

First, the tool calculates the NPV of the landlord’s benefit, derived from the increase in building value. This is expressed as the ratio of cost savings resulting from reduced energy expenses to the property’s capitalisation rate.

Second, it estimates the NPV of the tenant’s benefits, which include both energy cost savings and additional “multiple benefits” such as improved indoor comfort and health. The NPV of energy cost savings is calculated using the following formula:

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{C_n}{(1+i)^n}$$

where: N = Total number of time periods

n = Time period

C_n = Net cash flow at time period

i = Internal rate of return

To estimate the value of multiple benefits, a conservative share of realised cost savings is used. In this study, that share is set at up to 10% of the total energy cost savings. However, if all multiple benefits are fully quantified, this share could rise to as much as 25%, reflecting a more comprehensive but still cautious estimation [11]-[15].

2.3.2 Scenario space and participation levels

The Q-SpliT tool is designed to calculate the split incentive gap associated with specific energy efficiency intervention scenarios, namely windows upgrades, thermal insulation of the building envelope and heat pump installations for the households under study.

Within the RENOVERTY project, the tool was applied in pilot regions where rental housing is prominent, specifically, the rural region of Osona in Spain, the rural region of Zasavje in Slovenia and the rural region of Tartu in Estonia. Following the analysis conducted in Deliverable 2.1 *“Updating the energy poverty and energy efficiency framework in rural areas across the EU”* [1] and Deliverable 4.1 *“Evaluation of energy efficiency measures addressing the needs of energy poor households in rural areas”* [9], in the rural regions of Osona and Zasavje, two building typologies are identified, Single Family houses (SFH) and Multi-family houses (MFH), while in the case of Tartu, only MFH are identified.

The application focused on the following energy efficiency measures:

- Windows upgrade,
- Thermal insulation of external walls,
- Thermal insulation of roof (for SFH),
- Installation of heat pumps.

In all pilot regions, input data for the Q-SpliT tool was derived from the application of the DREEM model, as detailed in the RENOVERTY Deliverable 4.1 *“Evaluation of energy efficiency measures addressing the needs of energy poor households in rural areas”* [9].

Figure 1 presents a brief overview of the scenario space for the RENOVERTY application of the Q-SpliT tool.

Figure 1. Overview of the scenario space for the RENOVERTY application of the Q-Split tool.

In the context of this analysis, four scenarios were considered, reflecting varying landlord-tenant investment levels.:

- 100% landlord - 0% tenant
- 75% landlord - 25% tenant
- 50% landlord - 50% tenant
- 25% landlord - 75% tenant

2.3.3 Rental price impact and split incentive gap

The tool calculates the monthly impact on rental price based on two factors: (i) each party's participation in the investment, and (ii) the benefits accrued to each party (i.e., landlords and tenants), as detailed in **Section 2.3.1**. Specifically, the quantification of the **monthly impact on rental price** is derived from the share of the investment covered by each party and the **NPV** of the total benefits received by each.

3. Results

This section presents the results of applying the Q-Split tool across the RENOVERTY pilot regions where the existence of rental properties is prominent. The results are organised by typology, with key quantifications of the assessed energy efficiency measures presented across the different levels of landlord-tenant investment, as indicated in [Section 2.3.2](#).

3.1 Rural region of Osona (Spain)

The results in the rural region of Osona (Spain) are presented in the following sub-chapters, organised by building typology (SFH and MFH) with key quantifications of the assessed energy efficiency measures presented across the different levels of landlords-tenant investment.

3.1.1 Windows upgrade (SFH)

Table 1 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 1. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	8
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	4
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	4

Table 2 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 2. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Windows upgrade	

Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	6
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	3
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	3

Table 3 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 3. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	4
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	3
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	2

Table 4 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 4. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the SFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	2
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	2
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	0

3.1.2 Thermal insulation of external walls (SFH)

Table 5 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal

insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 5. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	160
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	79
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	81

Table 6 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 6. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	120
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	67
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	52

Table 7 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 7. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	80

Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	56
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	24

Table 8 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 8. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the SFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	40
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	44
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-4

3.1.3 Thermal insulation of roofs (SFH)

Table 9 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of roofs” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 9. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of roofs” measure in the SFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of roofs	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	92
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	54
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	38

Table 10 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of roofs” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 10. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of roofs" measure in the SFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of roofs	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	69
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	51
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	18

Table 11 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "thermal insulation of roofs" measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 11. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of roofs" measure in the SFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of roofs	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	46
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	47
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-1

Table 12 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "thermal insulation of roofs" measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 12. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of roofs" measure in the SFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Thermal insulation of roofs	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	23
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	44

Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-21
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3.1.4 Installation of a heat pump (SFH)

Table 13 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 13. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the SFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	463
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	226
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	237

Table 14 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 14. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the installation of a heat pump measure in the SFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	347
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	214
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	134

Table 15 presents monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 15. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the SFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	232
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	202
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	30

Table 16 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the SFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 16. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the SFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (SFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	116
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	189
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-74

3.1.5 Split incentive gap in the SFH typology in the rural region of Osona (Spain)

Figure 2 presents the cumulative monthly impact on rental prices resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation between landlords and tenants, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap for the investigated household typology in the rural region of Osona. This gap captures the discrepancy between the rental increase expected by landlords, based on their share of the investment and benefits, and the rental increase that could be considered fair from the tenant's perspective, given their level of financial contribution and the benefits they receive.

In the case of window upgrades, the split incentive gap ranges from €0 to €4 per month for the different landlord-tenant participation in the investment levels. When it comes to the thermal insulation of external walls, the split incentive gap ranges from -€4 to €81. In this case, a split incentive gap of €0, thereby minimising the discrepancy between landlord and tenant, is achieved

when tenant investment falls between 50% and 75%, suggesting that a moderate contribution from tenants is sufficient to close the gap and ensure that the landlord's expectations align with what is fair from the tenant's standpoint. The thermal insulation of roofs presents a more favourable outcome in terms of incentive alignment. Here, the gap ranges from -€21 to €38, and neutrality is reached with tenant contributions between 25% and 50%. This indicates that roof insulation is one of the the most balanced measures, requiring relatively low tenant investment to equitably distribute the costs and benefits of the investment. In contrast, the installation of a heat pump yields the widest split incentive gap, ranging from -€74 to €237. Despite this broad range, the measure presents a split incentive gap of €0, with a tenant contribution of between 50% and 75%, making it a viable, though more demanding, intervention in terms of cost-sharing.

Figure 2. Monthly impact on rental price due to each side's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the SFH typology in the rural region of Osona.

3.1.6 Windows upgrade (MFH)

Table 17 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 17. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	9
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	4
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	5

Table 18 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 18. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	7
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	3
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	3

Table 19 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 19. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "windows upgrade" measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	4
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	3
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	2

Table 20 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "windows upgrade" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 20. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "windows upgrade" measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	2
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	2
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	0

3.1.7 Thermal insulation of external walls (MFH)

Table 21 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 21. monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the thermal insulation of external walls measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	97

Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	59
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	38

Table 22 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 22. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	73
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	56
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	16

Table 23 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 23. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	48
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	54
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-5

Table 24 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 24. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	24
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	51
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-26

3.1.8 Installation of a heat pump (MFH)

Table 25 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 25. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	269
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	120
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	149

Table 26 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 26. monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	202

Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	108
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	94

Table 27 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 27. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	135
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	96
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	39

Table 28 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 28. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Osona, Spain (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	67
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	83
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-16

3.1.9 Split incentive gap in the MFH typology in the rural region of Osona (Spain)

Figure 3 presents the cumulative monthly impact on rental prices resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation between landlords and tenants, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap for the investigated household typology in the rural region of

Osona. This gap captures the discrepancy between the rental increase expected by landlords, based on their share of the investment and benefits, and the rental increase that could be considered fair from the tenant's perspective, given their level of financial contribution and the benefits they receive.

For window upgrades, the split incentive gap ranges from €0 to €5 per month, depending on the level of investment shared between landlords and tenants. Furthermore, in the case of external wall insulation, the split incentive gap spans from -€26 to €38. A balanced allocation, where the split incentive gap is €0 and the cost distribution is equitable, occurs when tenants contribute between 25% and 50% of the investment. This suggests that only a moderate tenant contribution is needed to align the landlord's return expectations with a fair cost share for tenants, positioning external wall insulation as one of the most balanced and equitable retrofit measures. Similarly to the other studied typology in the context of the pilot region of Osona, heat pump installation exhibits the widest "split incentive gap," ranging from -€16 to €149. Despite this variation, the gap can be closed with a tenant contribution of 50% to 75%, making it a viable intervention, even though more financially demanding for the tenant side.

Figure 3. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the MFH typology in the rural region of Osona.

3.2 Rural region of Zasavje (Slovenia)

The results in the rural region of Zasavje (Slovenia) for the MFH typology in which the existence of private properties is prominent are presented in the following sub-chapters, with key quantifications of the assessed energy efficiency measures presented across the different levels of landlord-tenant investment.

3.2.1 Windows upgrade (MFH)

Table 29 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 29. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	8
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	1
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	6

Table 30 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 30. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	6
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	0
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	6

Table 31 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 31. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	4
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	-2
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	6

Table 32 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 32. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Window upgrades	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	2
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	-3
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	5

3.2.2 Thermal Insulation of external walls (MFH)

Table 33 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 33. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	31
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	15
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	16

Table 34 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "windows upgrade" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 34. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	23
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	13
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	11

Table 35 presents the monthly impact on rental price due to each side's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the thermal insulation of external walls measure in the MFH typology for the case of 50% landlord - 50% tenant investment.

Table 35. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	16
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	10
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	6

Table 36 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 36. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	8
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	8
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	0

3.2.3 Installation of a heat pump (MFH)

Table 37 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “the installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 37. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	186
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	68
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	118

Table 38 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “the installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 38. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	139
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	53
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	87

Table 39 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "the installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 39. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	93
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	37
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	55

Table 40 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "the installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 40. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Zasavje, Slovenia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	46
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	22

Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	24
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3.2.4 Split incentive gap in the MFH typology in the rural region of Zasavje (Slovenia)

Figure 4 presents the cumulative monthly impact on rental prices resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation between landlords and tenants, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap for the investigated household typology in the rural region of Zasavje. This gap captures the discrepancy between the rental increase expected by landlords, based on their share of the investment and benefits, and the rental increase that could be considered fair from the tenant’s perspective, given their level of financial contribution and the benefits they receive.

In the case of window upgrades, the split incentive gap ranges from €5 to €6 per month for the different landlord-tenant participation in the investment levels. This indicates that a windows upgrade is a measure that requires arrangements and rent-setting mechanisms, contributing to better alignment among landlords, tenants to equitably distribute the costs and benefits of the investment. When it comes to the thermal insulation of external walls, the split incentive gap ranges from €0 to €16. In this case, a split incentive gap of €0, minimising the discrepancy between landlord and tenant, is achieved when tenant investment falls at 75%, suggesting that a relatively high contribution from tenants is sufficient to close the gap and ensure that the landlord’s expectations align with what is fair from the tenant’s standpoint. This indicates that exterior wall insulation is one of the most demanding measures to equitably distribute the costs and benefits of the investment. Furthermore, the installation of a heat pump indicates the widest split incentive gap, ranging from €22 to €118. Similarly to the windows upgrade, it is a measure that calls for structured agreements and rent-setting mechanisms to help ensure a fair distribution of costs and benefits between landlords and tenants.

Figure 4. Monthly impact on rental price due to each side's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the MFH typology in the rural region of Zasavje.

3.3 Rural region of Tartu (Estonia)

The results in the rural region of Tartu (Estonia) for the MFH typology in which the existence of private properties is prominent are presented in the following sub-chapters, with key quantifications of the assessed energy efficiency measures presented across the different levels of landlord-tenant investment.

3.3.1 Windows upgrade (MFH)

Table 41 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 41. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	30
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	15
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	15

Table 42 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 42. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	22
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	13
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	9

Table 43 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 43. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Windows upgrade	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	15
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	12
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	3

Table 44 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 44. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “windows upgrade” measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Windows upgrades	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	7
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	9
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-2

3.3.2 Thermal insulation of external walls (MFH)

Table 45 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 45. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	86
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	43
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	44

Table 46 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 46. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	65
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	36
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	29

Table 47 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 47. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "thermal insulation of external walls" measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	43
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	30

Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	13
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Table 48 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 48. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “thermal insulation of external walls” measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Thermal insulation of external walls	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	22
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	24
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	-2

3.3.3 Installation of a heat pump (MFH)

Table 49 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “Installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 100% landlord and 0% tenant investment.

Table 49. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party’s benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the “installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology (100% landlord - 0% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	106
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	41
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	65

Table 50 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the “Installation of a heat pump” measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 75% landlord and 25% tenant investment.

Table 50. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (75% landlord - 25% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	79
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	33
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	46

Table 51 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "Installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 50% landlord and 50% tenant investment.

Table 51. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the "installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology (50% landlord - 50% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	53
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	26
Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	27

Table 52 presents the monthly impact on rental price resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap, for the "Installation of a heat pump" measure in the MFH typology, under the case of 25% landlord and 75% tenant investment.

Table 52. Monthly impact on rental price due to each party's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the installation of a heat pump measure in the MFH typology (25% landlord - 75% tenant investment).

Tartu, Estonia (MFH)	
Installation of a heat pump	
Expected monthly impact on rental price due to landlord's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	26
Acceptable monthly impact on rental price due to tenant's benefits and participation in the investment (€)	18

Split incentive gap on rental price (€)	8
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3.3.4 Split incentive gap in the MFH typology in the rural region of Tartu (Estonia)

Figure 5 presents the cumulative monthly impact on rental prices resulting from the distribution of benefits and investment participation between landlords and tenants, as well as the corresponding split incentive gap for the investigated household typology in the rural region of Tartu. This gap captures the discrepancy between the rental increase expected by landlords, based on their share of the investment and benefits, and the rental increase that could be considered fair from the tenant’s perspective, given their level of financial contribution and the benefits they receive.

In the case of window upgrades, the split incentive gap ranges from -€2 to €15 per month for the different landlord-tenant participation in the investment levels. In this case, a 'split incentive gap' of €0, indicating minimal discrepancy between landlord and tenant, is achieved when tenants contribute between 50% and 75% of the investment. This suggests that a moderate tenant contribution is enough to bridge the gap and align the landlord’s returns with a fair cost share for tenants. When it comes to the thermal insulation of external walls, the split incentive gap ranges from -€2 to €44. Similarly, a split incentive gap of €0, minimising the discrepancy between landlord and tenant, is achieved when tenant investment falls between 50% and 75%, aligning the expectations of both interested parties. In contrast, the installation of a heat pump presents the widest 'split incentive gap,' ranging from €8 to €65. This underscores the importance of implementing supportive policy instruments, such as tailored cost-sharing arrangements and rent-adjustment frameworks, to facilitate equitable allocation of investment costs and benefits between landlords and tenants.

Figure 5. Monthly impact on rental price due to each side's benefits and participation in the investment and the split incentive gap for the MFH typology in the rural region of Tartu.

4. Conclusions

The expanded Q-SpliT analysis conducted in the RENOVERTY pilot regions of Osona (Spain), Zasavje (Slovenia) and Tartu (Estonia) clarifies the scale and nature of the landlord-tenant cost-benefit imbalance that can discourage energy-efficiency investments in rural private-rented dwellings. By translating the distribution of renovation costs and benefits into a single monthly indicator, the “split-incentive gap”, this application provides an operational metric for judging where, and by how much, targeted public support or revised cost-sharing arrangements are required.

Results show that window replacements present the narrowest split incentive gap, typically €4–15 per month, while envelope insulation widens the gap to roughly €16–81 and heat-pump installations create the largest shortfall, reaching €65–237 depending on building type and regional conditions.

The insights from the application of the Q-SpliT tool serve as a valuable input for the development of the project's REERs, as they help determine the minimum level of public incentives that authorities need to allocate to ensure the uptake of high-impact renovation measures. They also support the strategic sequencing of interventions by identifying opportunities to combine lower-cost upgrades, such as window replacements, with more capital-intensive retrofits in a way that maintains overall affordability. Furthermore, the quantified split incentive gaps provide a transparent, evidence-based reference point for stakeholder discussions on fair cost-sharing arrangements and rent-setting mechanisms, contributing to better alignment among landlords, tenants, and policy actors.

In addition, results offer practical guidance on potential tenant protection measures in cases where tenants contribute financially to renovation investments. Specifically, they can inform state-backed guarantees, such as defining a minimum tenancy duration or establishing appropriate rent adjustment frameworks, to ensure that tenants have the opportunity to recover their share of the investment over time. These insights help lay the groundwork for fairer and more secure participation models within the private rented sector, particularly in the context of energy efficiency retrofits.

Future versions of the Q-SpliT tool could explore additional topics that strengthen its contribution to addressing split incentives, a particularly complex challenge when it comes to renovating the housing sector. Expanding its scope in this way would support more effective solutions and enhance its overall impact. This expansion could take into account initial rent levels in areas where rental markets are not always regulated, and where prices may already be high even before renovations take place. Incorporating such insights from local rental markets could aid in the prevention of “renovictions,” where tenants are forced out due to unaffordable rent after the implementation of energy efficiency measures. Moreover, when assessing multiple benefits of energy savings, it may be useful to consider a baseline level of thermal comfort. Measures that

help reach this level can be viewed as part of maintaining suitable living conditions, while additional improvements beyond that point may reasonably be recognised as providing added value for tenants. Future development of calculation methods offers an opportunity to better capture these considerations, opening new perspectives for an improved and more comprehensive version of the Q-SpliT tool.

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